

Effect of Utilizing Foundry Sand as Mineral Filler in Bituminous Concrete Mixture Design

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Abstract: Bituminous concrete is one of the most expensive and high-priced flexible pavement layers utilized in surface courses. The bituminous mixtures are effectively designed to meet the design criteria of stability and durability despite their high material cost. Mineral filler that has passed through a 0.075 mm sieve plays an essential function in bituminous mixtures. The Asphalt Institute suggests using 4 to 8% filler in asphalt concrete. Common filler materials, such as cement, lime stone, granite powder, and so on, are not easily and affordably available in India. In India, foundry sand is thought to be less expensive and more abundant. The purpose of this study is to determine the influence of Foundry sand mineral filler on the behaviour of bituminous concrete mixtures. For the comparison, the Marshall procedure of mixture design was adopted. Marshall stabilities of mixtures with 25, 50, 75, and 100 percent foundry sand (FSMF) and traditional mineral filler (IBPMF0) were determined to be 23.07 KN, 23.25 KN, 23.72 KN, 23.89 KN, and 23.16 KN, respectively, satisfying the Marshall Design minimum requirements of 9 KN. The study suggests that FSMF might be used as mineral filler in bituminous mixtures.

IndexTerms - Foundry sand, Mineral Filler, SEM, EDXA, Stability, Marshall Quotient

I. INTRODUCTION

Bituminous roads are those in which bitumen is used as a binder. It is made up of a compact mixture of aggregates, mineral filler, and bitumen. The type and amount of mineral filler material utilized has an impact on the quality and sustainability of bituminous roads. By being finely distributed in the bituminous cement, the mineral filler serves to stiffen it [1]. As filler in bituminous mixtures, various materials like as cement, lime, granite powder, stone dust, and fine sand are commonly utilized. Cement, Quarry stone dust, lime and Granite stone dust are more costly and can be utilized more efficiently for other application. Stone dust, Fly ash, and construction waste dust finer than 0.075 mm sieve size seemed to be effective as filler material. Several research projects have focused on the use of industrial by-products as mineral filler in bituminous mixtures during the last few years. Phosphate waste mineral filler (MF) [2], Jordanian oil shale fly ash (SFA) [3] [4], bag house fines (BHF) [5] [6], municipal solid waste ash (MSWA) [7], and ceramic waste [7] have all been examined as fillers. It was found that various types of recycled filler may be utilized in bituminous mixtures to increase performance. As a result, the current research work was undertaken to evaluate the behaviour of bituminous mixtures utilizing Foundry sand mineral filler (FSMF). When filler is mixes with less bitumen than is necessary to fill its air voids, a stiff dry product that is nearly unworkable results. Overfilling with bitumen, on the other hand, gives the mixture a flow character. The filler can improve particle resistance to movement within the mix matrix and/or function as an ingredient when it interfaces with the bituminous cement to modify the characteristics of the mastic [8]. The inclusion of mineral filler can improve the elastic modulus of an bituminous concrete mixture [9]. However, too much filler might weaken the mixture by increasing the quantity of bitumen required to lubricate the stones [10] [11]. Gradations also influence the impact of these fillers.

II. EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

2.1 Materials

The aggregate gradation [13] in our research work is summarized in Table 1.

In this investigation, the VG-30-viscosity grade from the MRPL oil refinery was used [14]. The properties of VG-30 bitumen are presented in Table 2.

The grain size analysis (GSD) of Foundry sand is shown in Figure 1.

2.2 Objectives and methodology

The study work's aims are to analyze the potentiality of molding industry by-products as mineral fillers (FSMF) in Bituminous concrete mid limit grade 2 mixes by laboratory examination. The morphology and chemical properties of the foundry sand mineral filler are examined using SEM (Scanning Electron Microscopes) and EDXA (Energy Dispersing X-ray Analyzers). Marshall volumetric (Voids analysis) and mechanistic characteristics (stability and flow) of BC-2 mixtures containing 0, 25, 50, 75, and 100 percent FSMF were also examined [12].

Table 1. Aggregate gradation for Bituminous concrete grading – 2 mixtures

IS Sieve size (mm)	Range of gradation	Percentage Retained on sieve sizes (Mid limit)	Percent of FSMF content
19	100	10.5	
13.2	79-100	10.5	
9.5	70-88	17	
4.75	53-71	12	
2.36	42-58	9	
1.18	34-48	9	
0.6	26-38	9	
0.3	18-28	7	
0.15	12-20	9	
0.075	4-10	7	0, 25, 50, 75 & 100

Table 2. Properties of VG-30

Description	Results
Penetration value @ 25°C, 0.1mm	68.33
Softening point in °C	51.75
Ductility value @ 27 °C in cm	82.5
Specific gravity(Sp.gr) @ 27 °C	1.00
Flash Point in °C	260.0
Viscosity test @ 135°C in cst	390.0

Table 3. Physical properties of materials

Test	Test Results
Sp.Gr. of FSMF	2.23
Specific surface area of FSMF, cm ² /gm	2775
Specific surface area of Cement, cm ² /gm	3181
Specific surface area of stone MF, cm ² /gm	2838

Fig. 1. Grain size distribution for Foundry sand materials

Fig. 2. SEM micrographs of FSMF

Table 4. Elemental composition of FS material

Element Line	Weight, %	Atom, %
C K	9.60	15.83
O K	36.24	44.88
F K	2.23	2.33
Al K	11.35	8.33
Si K	40.58	28.63
Si L	----	----
Total	100	100

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The findings of the Marshal Experiments on bituminous concrete grading-2 mixtures prepared with varying industrial by-product percentage by foundry sand mineral filler (FSMF) are presented in Table 5. The optimal binder content was selected from the test results for bituminous concrete grading-2 mixtures using 0, 25, 50, 75, and 100 percent foundry sand mineral fillers. The effect of foundry sand mineral fillers on the different parameters of bituminous concrete grading-2 mixtures has been described in the following sections.

Table 5 Mixture Parameters relative to 4 percent air voids for FSMF

Marshall Parameters	Type of MF	FSMF content, Percentage				
		0	25	50	75	100
Optimal bitumen content, %	FSMF	5.48	5.42	5.40	5.40	5.36
Air voids, %	FSMF	4.17	4.21	3.98	3.86	3.88
Marshall Stability, KN	FSMF	23.16	23.07	23.25	23.72	23.89
Flow, mm	FSMF	3.63	3.60	3.57	3.53	3.47
Bulk Density, g/cc	FSMF	2.37	2.37	2.37	2.37	2.35
Voids in Mineral Aggregates, %	FSMF	17.18	17.07	16.79	16.64	16.46
Voids Filled with Bitumen, %	FSMF	75.75	75.32	76.29	76.80	76.41
Theoretical Specific Density, g/cc	FSMF	2.48	2.48	2.47	2.46	2.44
Marshall Quotient, KN/mm	FSMF	6.37	6.41	6.52	6.71	6.89

3.1 Effect of FSMF on optimal bitumen content

As shown in Figure 3 below, the optimal bitumen content (OBC) of mixtures, designed with 0, 25, 50, 75 and 100 percent FSMF. The OBC assessed using 0, 25, 50, 75 and 100 per cent of IBP-MF shows a similar pattern as the FSMF content in the BC-2 mixture increases and the OBC decreases. It is also identified that the OBC referring to 4 per cent air void is marginally lower for BC-2 mixtures with 25, 50, 75 and 100 per cent FSMF compared to BC-2 mixtures with 0 per cent IBP-MF. This may be due to lower specific surface area of FSMF particle in mixture reduced the OBC when compared to traditional material.

Figure 3 Effect of FSMF on optimal bitumen content

3.2 Effect of FSMF on Marshall Stability value

It is observed from the Figure 4 that the BC-2 mixtures using FSMF showed high stability value as the FSMF content in the BC-2 mixture increases. It is also found that the stability value higher for BC-2 mixtures with 25, 50, 75 and 100 per cent FSMF compared to BC-2 mixtures with traditional mixtures (0 per cent IBPMF).

Figure 4 Effect of Foundry Sand MF on Marshall Stability value

3.3 Effect of FSMF on Flow value

Figure 5 showing the variation of flow value with 0, 25, 50, 75 and 100 per cent of FSMF. It is found that the Flow value of mixture decrease as the FSMF increases in the BC-2 mixture. This is because of lower specific surface area, irregular shape and rough textured FSMF particle replacing sub-rounded shape particle of traditional material in the mixture.

Figure 5 Effect of Foundry sand MF on Marshall Flow value

3.4 Effect of FSMF on Bulk Density

The effect of FSMF on the bulk density of the compacted BC-2 mixtures is shown in the Figure 6. BC-2 mixtures with FSMF content has decreased bulk density values compare to traditional mineral filler material. This is due to fact that the specific gravity of foundry sand mineral filler and theoretical specific gravity of mixture are lower than the BC-2 mixture with traditional materials (cement and stone dust).

Figure 6 Effect of IBP-MF on Bulk Density

IV. CONCLUSION

The following are some insights from the investigation of the mixture design characteristics of bituminous mixtures utilizing FSMF, and traditional materials.

- Based on the obtained digital image by SEM micrographs of mineral filler (MF) of FS material are very rough in surface texture and angular in shape compared to conventional materials.
- FS materials as MF provides effective interlocking and friction in the bituminous concrete mixtures which result in higher Marshall stability value compared to conventional mixtures.
- Foundry sand mineral filler has reduced the optimal bitumen content of bituminous concrete mixtures due to its low specific surface area and good interlocking properties (angular and rough texture of foundry sand mineral filler particle).
- The bituminous concrete mixture containing FSMF has significantly lowered the optimal bitumen content, which reduces the cost of production compare to bituminous concrete mixture of traditional material.
- High percentage of Silica and atom percentage (EDXA) in foundry sand, which enhances the Marshall stability value as seen in Marshall test results.
- The incorporation of FSMF to the grade-2 mixture of bituminous concrete significantly improved Marshall Stability value compare to traditional mixtures.

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